

Enhancing Consumer Purchase Intentions: Key Drivers in ShopeeFood's Online Food Delivery Service

Alma Aviona Imani¹, Refi Rifaldi Windya Giri²

^{1,2} Management Business Telecommunication and Informatics, Telkom University, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This study explores the multifaceted nature of consumer purchase intentions within the online food delivery sector, specifically for ShopeeFood. By examining the influences of social influence, effort expectancy, performance expectancy, trust, and food safety risk perception, the research provides valuable insights into the drivers behind customer decisions. The study employed a quantitative research method, utilizing a non-probability sampling technique with 277 respondents who completed an online survey. The findings reveal that social influence significantly enhances both effort and performance expectations, driving higher purchase intentions. Effort expectancy directly impacts performance expectations and purchase intentions, underscoring the importance of ease of use. Trust emerges as a critical factor, boosting purchase intentions and reducing food safety concerns. Interestingly, while food safety is important, it does not significantly deter purchase intentions, highlighting that consumers prioritize convenience and reliability. These insights can guide service providers in improving user experience and building stronger customer relationships.

KEYWORDS: Online food delivery, social influence, effort expectancy, performance expectancy, consumer trust.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The development of technology and internet-based platforms has significantly impacted the evolution of our era and the marketing of products. Rapid technological advancements have brought about various media that facilitate consumers' search for information during the purchasing process (Indrawati et al., 2023). Feedback, or user perspectives, play a crucial role in marketing and promoting products electronically. This form of electronic word-of-mouth significantly influences customers, as they seek background information on products or services to feel safer and more comfortable with their purchasing decisions (Donthu, 2021; Yohansyah et al., 2022). Positive or negative feedback from prospective or former customers about a product or service available on the internet shapes how other customers perceive it (Balqis & Giri, 2023). The internet has created opportunities for entrepreneurs to market their products or services through applications that offer practical solutions, such as delivery without direct contact. Consumers can conveniently place orders through an application, which is particularly beneficial for online food delivery services (Tsai et al., 2023). In Indonesia, the online food delivery industry has grown rapidly, driven by consumer purchase intentions (Hong & Choi, 2023). Social media marketing is used to increase consumer knowledge about brands and foster positive perceptions (Prameswari & Giri, 2022). Shopee, a prominent e-commerce company, has ventured into the online food delivery market with its service, ShopeeFood. Despite being newly established in 2021, ShopeeFood has quickly gained traction, leveraging the high number of Shopee app users in Indonesia to become a popular choice for food delivery services (Adi, 2022). However, existing competitors like GoFood from Gojek and GrabFood from Grab indicate that ShopeeFood has not yet dominated the market. Nevertheless, the convenience of online food delivery services offers significant benefits to restaurants and consumers, despite potential risks related to food temperature control, hygiene, delivery conditions, user interface design, communication speed, and privacy (Yeo et al., 2021). Digital payment methods, such as digital wallets or e-wallets, have become standard in online food delivery transactions (Sisilia & Giri, 2020). Building trust through reliable service is crucial for increasing customer satisfaction and loyalty, which ultimately enhances long-term profitability (Hong et al., 2023). While previous studies have examined various aspects of consumer purchase intentions in online food delivery, there has been limited research specifically focused on ShopeeFood. Studies such as those by Hong et al. (2023) on determinants of customer purchase intentions, Roh et al. (2019) on the adoption of food messaging services in South Korea, and Yeo et al. (2021) on servitization of food applications, highlight the need for further investigation into the factors influencing consumer purchase intentions for ShopeeFood's service.

The rapid development of information technology and the internet has significantly impacted consumer behavior in obtaining products and services, particularly in the online food delivery service industry. ShopeeFood, a key player in this market, leverages this trend to facilitate food ordering via digital platforms. This research aims to investigate the impact of social influence, effort expectancy, performance expectancy, food safety risk perception, and trust on consumer purchasing interests. Additionally, it explores the relationship between trust and food safety risk perception within the context of ShopeeFood's online food delivery service.

The study employs a quantitative research method using a non-probability sampling technique and purposive sampling model. Data was collected through a survey questionnaire targeting online food delivery consumers in Indonesia. Data analysis was conducted using SmartPLS version 4, including descriptive analysis to understand respondent characteristics. The results indicate that social influence, effort expectancy, performance expectancy, and trust significantly influence purchase intention. Conversely, food safety risk perception has an insignificant and negative impact on purchase intention.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Today's advances in information and communication technology (ICT) have changed the way organizations do business, from growth in the e-commerce sector to data technology driving the application of new technologies in the organizational world. Unified Theory of Acceptance Use of Technology is a model developed to predict the intentions of consumer behavior and use of technology that focuses on consumer perspectives as well as decision-making in the use of technologies. (Alfanur & Kadono, 2019). With the UTAUT theory introduced by Venkatesh et al., (2003) which is a theoretical model to suggest that the actual use of technology is determined by behavioral values, there is a direct effect of the four main constructions that determine the possibility of the use of the technology, namely performance expectancy, effort expectance, social influence, and facilitating conditions as well as age, gender, experience, and preference of use affect predictive effects. (Marikyan et al., 2023). Based on the perspectives of previous research, the study aims to combine two key constructions (trust and food safety risk perception) into three key factors of the UTAUT, namely performance expectancy, effort expectance, and social influence, to improve prediction of factors affecting the intensity of purchases towards online food delivery. (Hong et al., 2023).

Social influences such as friends and family influence human behavior, there are negative and positive social influences, which positively influence the effort expectancy in the use of social media (Hong et al., 2023). Social media influence on services, known as performance expectancies, such as the internal trust of individuals, internal trust can be formed from the trust of the reference group (family, friends, or colleagues) in other words information from outside parties received by an individual then made as an opinion that facilitates recognition of the benefits of the service. (Hong et al., 2023). According to Yeo et al., (2021), social influence includes how one is influenced by others and how buyers see the importance of other people's beliefs about the kind of technology they use. Online food delivery requires customers to use technology such as a mobile application when making a booking, it is important to understand the customer's purchase intentions to be able to predict the way customers buy the goods (Hong et al., 2023).

According to Marikyan et al., (2023), effort expectancy is the level of ease of use of the system. In the use of online food delivery, if the service is used repeatedly, a previous study found that customers would feel comfortable using the service and feel that the service was useful, so the research showed that the effort expectancy had a positive influence on the intention to buy (Roh & Park, 2019). Customers indicate that they have a high intention to buy technology when customers feel that the use of the service is easy (Hong et al., 2023). Effort Expectancy or performance expectancy positively affects usability or ease of use, and both concepts are considered equal in terms of meaning. As a result, some settings that use new technologies, such as the mode image search application, have shown a positive impact of effort expectations on performance expectations (Hong et al., 2023).

An important role in performance expectancy is in the use of any product or service that customers believe will increase productivity or motivation of their purchases (Hong et al., 2023). Lee et al. (2019) on online food delivery, the relationship between performance anticipation and intention to buy a service or product, and Hong et al, (2021) that performance expectance is a determinant of the intention of purchase, there are online food deliveries.

A trust is a customer's trust in the parties involved in the transaction process because they are fair, secure, reliable, and provide security (Yeo et al., 2021). A trust in consumer confidence in the seller will be on an online food delivery arrangement, that the trust of the customer is expressed as confidence that the online food delivery can be reliable (Hong et al, 2023). Belief in technology and

service providers can help customers in the convenience of their services, customers who shop online find convenience after trusting a seller who sells online. (Hong et al., 2023).

Food requirement is very much needed by society, when consuming food, society is not completely free from danger. Risk from food affects customer behavior called food safety risk perception (Hong et al., 2023). Belief is very influential in food safety risk perception, where taking a purchase intention can change belief if the food ordered is unsafe. (Yeo et al., 2021). In a study, Ha et al., (2020) stated that consumers do not feel safe with food suppliers.

Consumer behavior is an individual or group (consumer) behavior or action when buying or using goods and services, which includes a decision-making process to ensure that consumers get the goods or services they want. (Nugraha et al., 2021). According to Kotler et al., (2022) in consumer behavior, there are two common factors in which consumers make evaluations that can interfere between the intention to buy and the purchase intention, the first factor is the attitude of other individuals (the intensity of other people's perception of the options we can choose and the desire of ourselves to follow others), the second factor is a situation analysis that allows to appear to change the state of the intentions to buy.

Figure 2.1. Conceptual Framework

Following the conceptual framework depicted in Figure 2.1, the following hypothesis was established for this investigation.

- H_1: Social influence positively influences effort expectancy.
- H_2: Social influence has a positive influence on performance expectancy.
- H_3: Social influence is positive to purchase intention.
- H_4: Effort expectancy has a positive effect on performance expectance.
- H_5: Effort expectancy has a positive influence on purchase intention.
- H_6: Performance expectancy has a positive influence on purchase intention.
- H_7: Trust has a positive influence on effort expectancy.
- H_8: Trust has a positive influence on performance expectancy.
- H_9: Trust restricts positive interests due to purchase intention.
- H_10: Trust negatively affects food safety risk perception.
- H_11: Food safety risk perception has a negative influence on purchase intention.

3.0 METHOD AND RESULT

3.1 Method

This study employs a quantitative research method, which is characterized by its systematic approach and ability to handle complex variations by examining a large number of samples to measure causality (Sahir, 2021). The focus of this correlation study is on the influence of several variables—Social Influence (X1), Effort Expectancy (X2), Performance Expectancy (X3), Trust (X4), and Food Safety Risk Perception (X5)—on Purchase Intention (Y1).

The sampling technique used is non-probability sampling, where not all members of the population have an equal chance of being selected (Dubey & D.P. Kothari, 2022). This study applies a onetailed test with a 95% confidence level, utilizing a Z value of 1.645 from the distribution table with an alpha of 0.05 (Hikmawati, 2020).

A total of 275 respondents participated in the study, selected based on a questionnaire distributed on social media. The criteria for participation included being a Shopee e-commerce user, of any gender, aged 17 years and above. Respondents were asked to complete a 22-item questionnaire tailored to the specified indicator variables.

For data analysis, the study used Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) based on covariance techniques, with the software SmartPLS version 4.0. Partial Least Squares (PLS), an SEM method, was chosen for its ability to address issues such as missing data and multicollinearity (Sholihin & Ratmono, 2021).

3.2 Result

The data collection process for this study involved 277 respondents, exceeding the minimum requirement of 275. The characteristics of the respondents were determined based on gender, age, and educational background. Primary data was collected through online platforms using Google Forms, which were distributed via social media channels such as WhatsApp, Instagram, and X.

Among the 277 respondents, women dominated the sample, accounting for 63.2%. This suggests that women are the primary users of online food delivery services. The age distribution revealed that the majority of respondents, 61.8%, were between 17 and 23 years old. This indicates that young adults in this age group are the predominant users of Shopee and ShopeeFood services. In terms of educational background, 58.7% of respondents had completed higher secondary school, and 58.8% were students. This highlights that students, who are typically more familiar with internet and e-commerce platforms, constituted the largest group of participants. Descriptive analysis of the data showed high average values for effort expectancy, performance expectancy, trust, and purchase intention, with all these variables scoring above 4. This indicates that respondents generally view the ease of use, service performance, trustworthiness, and desire to buy ShopeeFood services positively. The low deviation rates for most items suggest consistent perceptions among respondents. However, the food safety risk perception variable had an average value below 4, indicating some concerns about food safety in online food delivery services. The higher standard deviation for this variable points to greater variation in respondent perceptions.

Overall, these findings provide valuable insights for ShopeeFood, highlighting both strengths and areas for improvement. The data underscores the importance of addressing food safety concerns to enhance consumer trust and satisfaction.

3.3 Measurement Model

To test model identification, construction validity, and construction reliability, measurement model testing is carried out. Convergent validity was evaluated using loading factor values > 0,700 and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) > 0,500 (Hardani et al., 2020). (Sholihin dan Ratmono, 2021). A construct reliability test is performed to assess the reliability of each indicator item and ensure the stability of the measurement (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). The reliability tests use Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability, each of which must be higher than 0.7. (Hardani et al., 2020). The goodness of fit test measures the conformity of the model with the data through the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) value < 0.08, the Normed Fit Index (NFI) > 0.90, and the rms_Theta value approaching 0 (Dobey & Kothari, 2022).

Table 3.1. Convergent Validity

Construct (Variable)	Indicator	Loading Factor (>0,700)	Average Variance Extracted (AVE) (>0,500)	Description
Social Influence	SI1	0,879	0,788	Valid
	SI2	0,896		Valid
Effort Expectancy	EE1	0,869	0,742	Valid
	EE2	0,882		Valid
	EE3	0,833		Valid
Performance Expectancy	PE1	0,850	0,734	Valid

	PE2	0,881		Valid
	PE3	0,839		Valid
Trust	TR1	0,872	0,768	Valid
	TR2	0,891		Valid
	TR3	0,866		Valid
Food Safety Risk Perception	FSRP1	0,898	0,828	Valid
	FSRP2	0,905		Valid
	FSRP3	0,925		Valid
Purchase Intention	PI1	0,846	0,721	Valid
	PI2	0,885		Valid
	PI3	0,814		Valid

Data processing results show that all variables in this study have been declared valid. The variables Social Influence (SI), Effort Expectancy (EE), Performance Expected (PE), Trust (TR), Food Safety Risk Perception (FSRP), and Purchase Intention (PI) have loading factor values greater than 0.700 for each indicator, so the indicators are considered valid. In addition, the six constructive or latency variables also have Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values higher than 0.500, indicating high validity. Overall, the research instruments used, both in the form of questions to measure the variable and the variables themselves, have qualified for validity and can be used for further analysis. Table 3.2. and the results show that different structures have higher values when compared to the correlation between structures, indicating a good discriminatory validity. These values indicate that different constructions are different from each other, which allows us to describe the phenomena measured in this study.

Table 3.2. Discriminant Validity

	Effort	FSRP	Performance	PI	Social	Trust
EE	0,861					
FSRP	0,273	0,910				
PE	0,831	0,363	0,857			
PI	0,851	0,295	0,854	0,849		
SI	0,718	0,308	0,755	0,787	0,888	
TR	0,836	0,287	0,787	0,837	0,762	0,876

The measurement of reliability is measured with composite realism (construction) and obtained that the value of the square root of each AVE structure is greater than its correlation value with other structures when comparing AVE and AVE root it is known that the validity value is good because the constructed structure is larger than the different structure and the value on the root of AVE on the diagonal column is bigger than that between variables on columns other than diagonal. It can then be concluded that the research meets the discriminant validity criteria. Table 3.3. and this study's constructs were all deemed reliable since the approach value is greater than 0.7 (Sholihin & Ratmono, 2021).

Table 3.3. Construct Reliability

Construct (Variable)	Cronbach's Alpha (>0,700)	Composite Reliability (>0700)	Description
Effort Expectancy	0,826	0,827	Reliable
Food Safety Risk Perception	0,896	0,902	Reliable

Performance Expectancy	0,818	0,818	Reliable
Purchase Intention	0,805	0,807	Reliable
Social Influence	0,731	0,734	Reliable
Trust	0,849	0,849	Reliable

The goodness of Fit is a random variable test that is studied following a particular distribution such as binomial, normal, or other distribution when the given data is given in a scatological form. (Dobey & Kothari, 2022). A model is specified to fit when the SRMR value is <0,08. The SRMR is a measure of the absolute mean value of the residual covariance. The calculation of the model stated fit is also derived from the NFI value <0.90. NFL is an additional match measure and NFI yields between 0 and 1, the closer to 1 (one), the better the match. It can be concluded from the Goodness of Fit test of this study that the result of Goodness Of Fit (GoF) in this study is stated as a large GoF because of SRMR <0.08 and NFI <0.90, which means that the PLS model in this research is good.

Table 3.4. The Goodness of Fit Test Result

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0,054	0,063
d_ ULS	0,439	0,607
d_ G	0,413	0,425
Chi-square	672,908	687,256
NFL	0,810	0,806

3.4 Structural Model

The research framework for this study is a replication of the Hong et al., (2023) journal, which discusses the issue of online food delivery and wants to look at the determining drivers of the customer's intention to buy the service. Figure 3.2 shows the results of this study's structural model processing.

Figure 2. Result of Structural Model Processing

The result of the R-Square calculation that describes Social Influence and Trust was able to explain Effort Expectancy of 71.5%, Food Safety Risk Perception of 8.2%, and Performance expectancy of 74.9%. At Purchase Intention the variables Social influence, Trust, Effort expectancy, Performance expectancies, and Food safety risk perceptions were able to describe Purchase Intent of up to 83.1% and obtained the highest value in the calculation of R-square. In Table 3.4. Shown the results of testing the research hypothesis.

Table 3.4. Hypothesis Test

Hypothesis	Effect	Path Coefficient	T-value	P-value	Description
H1	SI -> EE	0,193	2,901	0,004	H1 supported
H2	SI -> PE	0,274	4,908	***	H2 supported
H3	SI -> PI	0,190	3,030	0,002	H3 supported
H4	EE -> PE	0,503	7,353	***	H4 supported
H5	EE -> PI	0,268	3,619	***	H5 supported
H6	PE ->PI	0,320	5,082	***	H6 supported
H7	TR ->EE	0,689	10,402	***	H7 supported
H8	TR -> PE	0,157	1,921	0,055	H8 rejected
H9	TR -> PI	0,221	2,962	0,003	H9 supported
H10	TR -> FSRP	0,287	4,219	***	H10 supported
H11	FSRP -> PI	-0,016	0,580	0,562	H11 rejected

SI: Social Influence, **EE:** Effort Expectancy, **PE:** Performance Expectancy, **TR:** Trust, **FSRP:** Food Safety Risk Perception, **PI:** Purchase Intention
P-value * = 0,000**

Social Influence (SI) significantly impacts Effort Expectancy (EE) and Performance Expectancy (PE). The study reveals that social factors, such as peer recommendations and social proof, play crucial roles in shaping consumers' expectations of the effort required to use a service and their perceptions of its performance. This finding aligns with previous research by Yeo et al. (2021) and Hong et al. (2023), indicating that consumer purchasing value is heavily influenced by social networks and online reviews. Consequently, companies can leverage social media and influencer partnerships to enhance these perceptions, thereby increasing user engagement and purchase intentions.

Effort Expectancy (EE) not only directly influences Performance Expectancy (PE) but also significantly impacts Purchase Intention (PI). The study demonstrates that the easier a service is to use, the higher the consumers' expectations of its performance, which, in turn, increases their likelihood of purchasing. This correlation underscores the importance of user-friendly interfaces and seamless user experiences. Studies by Marikyan et al. (2023) and Lee et al. (2019) support this, emphasizing that simplicity and usability are critical in technology acceptance and customer satisfaction. Therefore, improving the ease of use of services can enhance customer perceptions of expected performance and satisfaction, ultimately leading to higher purchase intentions.

Trust (TR) emerges as a vital factor, significantly influencing Effort Expectancy (EE), Purchase Intention (PI), and reducing Food Safety Risk Perception (FSRP). High levels of trust lead consumers to believe that a service is easy to use and reliable, increasing their intention to use it. However, trust has a relatively weaker impact on Performance Expectancy (PE), suggesting the need for further research into additional contributing factors. Interestingly, while food safety is an important consideration, it does not significantly deter purchase intentions, as consumers prioritize convenience, performance, and trust over safety concerns. This finding is consistent with research by Hong et al. (2023), indicating that despite awareness of food safety risks, consumers trust

platforms to manage these risks effectively. Consequently, service providers should focus on building trust and ensuring high performance to boost customer purchase intentions.

4.0 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The study's findings underscore the multifaceted nature of consumer purchase intentions within the online food delivery sector, specifically for ShopeeFood. By dissecting the influence of social influence, effort expectancy, performance expectancy, and trust, we gain a clearer understanding of the drivers behind customer decisions.

The strong impact of social influence on both effort expectancy and performance expectancy suggests that peer recommendations and social proof play crucial roles in shaping consumer expectations. This aligns with the broader literature indicating that social networks and word-of-mouth significantly affect consumer behavior. Companies should leverage social media and influencer partnerships to enhance these perceptions, thereby increasing overall engagement and purchase intentions.

Effort expectancy's direct effect on performance expectancy and purchase intentions highlights the importance of user-friendly interfaces and seamless user experiences. As consumers increasingly seek convenience, platforms that prioritize ease of use are likely to see higher satisfaction and repeated usage. This finding is consistent with previous studies that emphasize the role of simplicity and usability in technology acceptance and customer loyalty.

Performance expectancy emerged as a critical determinant of purchase intentions, reinforcing the notion that perceived benefits and service performance drive future use. This underscores the need for companies to ensure their services meet consumer expectations in terms of reliability, speed, and overall efficiency. Enhancing these aspects can lead to higher customer retention and positive word-of-mouth.

Trust plays a significant role in influencing effort expectancy and purchase intentions, though its impact on performance expectancy is comparatively weaker. This indicates that while trust fosters confidence in the ease of use and reliability of the service, other factors may be more critical in shaping performance expectations. Companies should continue to build trust through transparent practices, reliable service, and strong customer support to maintain and grow their user base.

Interestingly, food safety risk perception does not significantly deter purchase intentions, suggesting that consumers prioritize other factors such as convenience, performance, and trust over safety concerns. While food safety remains important, it appears that its impact on the decisionmaking process is secondary to these other elements. This could be due to consumers' trust in the platforms to manage safety risks effectively.

This study highlights the multifaceted nature of consumer purchase intentions in the online food delivery sector, revealing the paramount importance of social influence, ease of use, perceived performance, and trust. These factors collectively drive customer engagement and intention to use services like ShopeeFood. While food safety remains a concern, it is secondary to the overall convenience and reliability perceived by consumers. To enhance customer acquisition and retention, service providers must focus on building trust, simplifying user experience, and ensuring high service performance. Future research should explore additional factors that shape performance expectations and adapt to evolving consumer behaviors in a post-pandemic world

5.0 RESEARCH CONTRIBUTION AND FUTURE RESEARCH OF THE STUDY

This study provides significant contributions to both academic research and practical applications within the online food delivery service industry.

On the academic front, this research deepens the understanding of how social influence, effort expectancy, performance expectancy, and trust shape purchase intentions in online food delivery services. It extends existing theories in consumer behavior and technology acceptance, offering empirical evidence that underscores the importance of these factors in influencing consumer decisions. Additionally, the findings present a robust framework for future research, particularly in exploring additional factors influencing performance expectancy and trust in online services. Researchers can build upon this study to examine the interplay of these variables with other emerging trends in digital consumer behavior.

From a practical perspective, the insights into effort expectancy and performance expectancy can help service providers enhance the usability and performance of their platforms, making them more user-friendly and efficient. Understanding the role of social influence can guide marketers in designing more effective social media and word-of-mouth marketing strategies. The findings on trust highlight the importance of building and maintaining consumer trust to enhance purchase intentions. Service providers can

focus on transparency, reliability, and security to foster trust among users. Addressing food safety concerns, even if they are not the primary decision factor, can further reassure customers and enhance their overall experience. Additionally, demographic insights, such as the significant influence of younger age groups and students, can help companies like ShopeeFood tailor their marketing efforts to target these specific consumer segments more effectively.

REFERENCES

1. Alfannur, F., & Kadono, Y. (2019). Analysis of E-commerce Purchase Intention and Decision in Java and Sumatra. 2019 International Conference on Information Management and Technology (ICIMTech). doi:10.1109/icimtech.2019.8843731
2. Balqis, S., & Giri, R. R. W. (2023). The influence of EWOM on the purchase intention of young consumers at online travel agents through the expansion on the information Adoption model (Case study on Traveloka, Tiket.Com, Agoda, Pegipegi, Airbnb). *Journal of Economics & Business*, 12(3), 1569–1580. <https://doi.org/10.52644/joeb.v12i3.227>
3. Chanmi Hong, Eun-Kyong (Cindy) Choi, Hyun-Woo (David) Joung, Determinants of customer purchase intention toward online food delivery services: The moderating role of usage frequency, *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, Volume 54, 2023, Pages 7687, ISSN 1447-6770, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhtm.2022.12.005>.
4. Dubey, U. K. B., & Kothari, D. P. (2022). *Research methodology: Techniques and Trends*. Chapman & Hall/CRC.
5. Ha, T. M., Shakur, S., & Pham, K. H. (2020). Linkages among food safety risk perception, trust and information: Evidence from Hanoi consumers. *Food Control*, 110, 106965. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2019.106965>
6. Hardani, Auliya, N. H., Andriani, H., Fardani, R. A., Ustiawaty, J., Utami, E. F., Sukmana, D. J., & Istiqomah, R. R. (2020). *Metode penelitian kualitatif & kuantitatif*. CV. Pustaka Ilmu.
7. Hikmawati, F. (2017b). *Metodologi penelitian*.
8. Hong, C., Choi, H., Choi, E., & Joung, H. (2021). Factors affecting customer intention to use online food delivery services before and during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 48, 509–518. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhtm.2021.08.012>
9. Hong, J., & Choi, D. (2023). Determinants of customer purchase intentions against online food delivery services: The role of frequency moderation of use. *Journal of Foodservice Business Research*.
10. Hong, J., Park, H. J., & Roh, S. (2023). The effect of trust on consumer behavior in online food delivery services. *Journal of Business Research*.
11. Indrawati, Prily Calista Putri Yones, Saravanan Muthaiyah, eWOM via the TikTok application and its influence on the purchase intention of somethinc products, *Asia Pacific Management Review*, Volume 28, Issue 2, 2023, Pages 174-184, ISSN 1029-3132, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmr.2022.07.007>.
12. Jinjiang, He. (2023). The impact of users' trust on intention to use the mobile medical platform: Evidence from China. *Frontiers in Public Health*, doi: 10.3389/fpubh.2023.1076367
13. Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2021). *Marketing Management*, Global Edition. Pearson Higher Ed.
13. Lee, S., Lee, K., & Lee, D. (2019). The relationship between performance expectancy and intention to buy a service or product in the context of online food delivery. *Journal of Service Management*.
14. Li, C., Miroso, M., & Bremer, P. (2020). Review of Online Food Delivery Platforms and their Impacts on Sustainability. *Sustainability*, 12(14), 5528. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12145528>
15. Marikyan, D., Papagiannidis, S., & Alamanos, E. (2023). Exploring the role of effort expectancy in technology acceptance. *Information Technology & People*.
16. Naveen Donthu, Satish Kumar, Neeraj Pandey, Nitesh Pandey, Akanksha Mishra, Mapping the electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) research: A systematic review and bibliometric analysis, *Journal of Business Research*, Volume 135, 2021, Pages 758-773, ISSN 01482963, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.07.015>.
17. Nugraha, H. P., Sari, P. P., & Fatmawati, A. (2021). Consumer behavior and factors influencing purchase intentions. *Journal of Consumer Studies*.
18. Pei-Hsuan Tsai, Chih-Jou Chen, Wei-Hung Hsiao, Chin-Tsai Lin, Factors influencing the consumers' behavioural intention to use online food delivery service: Empirical evidence from Taiwan, *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Volume 73, 2023, 103329, ISSN 0969-6989, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2023.103329>.

19. Prameswari, R. D., & Giri, R. R. W. (2022). The Effect of Social Media Marketing Activities on Purchase Intention With Brand Awareness, Brand Image, Brand Equity As Intervening Variables on Kopi Janji Jiwa in Bandung City. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Management Review*, October, 72-87.
20. Rohani, Rohani., Andi, Hadidu., Manda, Hm. (2023). Consumer Behavior: Components of Purchase Intention Products E-Commerce Perspective Maqāṣid Al-Sharī'ah. *JESI (Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah Indonesia)*, 13(2):198-198. doi: 10.21927/jesi.2023.13(2).198-209
21. Roh, M., & Park, K. (2019). Adoption of O2O food delivery services in South Korea: The moderating role of moral obligation in meal preparation. *International Journal of Information Management*, 47, 262–273. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2018.09.017>
22. Ruiying Cai, Xi Y. Leung, Mindset matters in purchasing online food deliveries during the pandemic: The application of construal level and regulatory focus theories, *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, Volume 91, 2020, 102677, ISSN 0278-4319, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2020.102677>.
23. Sahir, S. H. (2021c). Metodologi penelitian. PENERBIT KBM INDONESIA.
24. Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2016). Research methods for business: a skill-building approach 7th edition. In John Wiley & Sons eBooks <http://103.227.140.9/handle/123456789/18302>
25. Shashikala, K. (2023). Online Service Booking Platform with Payment Integration. doi: 10.59461/ijitra.v2i2.54
26. Sholihin, M., & Ratmono, D. (2021). Analisis SEM-PLS dengan WarpPLS 7.0 untuk hubungan nonlinier dalam penelitian sosial dan bisnis. Penerbit Andi.
27. Shrafat, Ali, Sair., Rizwan, Qaisar, Danish. (2018). Effect of performance expectancy and effort expectancy on the mobile commerce adoption intention through personal innovativeness among Pakistani consumers.
28. Sisilia, A. R., & Giri, R. R. W. (2020). ANALISIS PEMASARAN MEDIA SOSIAL UNTUK MENENTUKAN INFLUENCER DAN TOPIK PEMBICARAAN (Studi Kasus: Go-Pay dan OVO). *Jurnal Mitra Manajemen*, 4(7), 1036–1047. <https://doi.org/10.52160/ejmm.v4i7.422>
29. Souji Gopalakrishna Pillai, Woo Gon Kim, Kavitha Haldorai, Hak-Seon Kim, Online food delivery services and consumers' purchase intention: Integration of theory of planned behavior, theory of perceived risk, and the elaboration likelihood model, *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, Volume 105, 2022, 103275, ISSN 0278-4319, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2022.103275>.
30. Thuy Thu Nguyen, Hoa Thi Thanh Phan, Impact of COVID-19 anxiety on functional foods consuming intention: role of electronic word of mouth, *Heliyon*, Volume 8, Issue 11, 2022, e11344, ISSN 2405-8440, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e11344>.
31. Tugrul, U., Daim., Nuri, Basoglu., Banu, Kargin., Kenny, Phan. (2014). Service Innovation Adoption: the Case of Value-Added Mobile Services. *Journal of The Knowledge Economy*, doi: 10.1007/S13132-012-0113-8
32. Yeo, S. F., Tan, C. L., Teo, S. L., & Tan, K. H. (2021). The role of food apps servitization on repurchase intention: A study of FoodPanda. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 234, 108063. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2021.108063>
33. Yeo, V. C. S., Goh, S. K., & Rezaei, S. (2021). Consumer experiences, attitude, and behavioral intention toward online food delivery (OFD) services. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*.

Cite this Article: Alma Aviona Imani, Refi Rifaldi Windya Giri (2024). Enhancing Consumer Purchase Intentions: Key Drivers in ShopeeFood's Online Food Delivery Service. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 7(6), 4922-4931